

Normalised counts

PF3D7_0104300

PF3D7_0410000

PF3D7_0420300

PF3D7_0422900

PF3D7_0501300

PF3D7_0522300

PF3D7_1030200

PF3D7_1327300

PF3D7_1036300

PF3D7_1302100

